
Effects of Smoking on Cardiovascular System

Omar Elsaka^{a*} and Mostafa Tarek Ghazali^a

^a *Department of Cardiology, Faculty of Medicine, Mansoura Manchester Medical Program (MMMP), Mansoura University, Mansoura, Egypt.*

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Article Information

Open Peer Review History:

This journal follows the Advanced Open Peer Review policy. Identity of the Reviewers, Editor(s) and additional Reviewers, peer review comments, different versions of the manuscript, comments of the editors, etc are available here: <https://www.sdiarticle5.com/review-history/78455>

Review Article

Received 07 November 2021
Accepted 10 January 2022
Published 20 January 2022

ABSTRACT

Background: Smoking is a significant risk factor for heart disease and death, and it is widely acknowledged as one of the world's leading causes of death. Cigarette smoke contains over 4000 compounds, including nicotine and carbon monoxide (CO), both of which can affect the heart. These fundamental components of cigarette smoke promote oxidative stress, endothelial damage, and deactivation, and are linked to very high total cholesterol and triglyceride levels in the blood, as well as low levels of cardioprotective high-density lipoprotein. Smoking accelerates the development of atherosclerosis and heart disease by producing intravascular inflammation. Secondhand smoking causes atherosclerosis to vanish and raises the risk of heart attack, stroke, aortic aneurysm, and sudden death. Smoking can promote diabetes and hasten the onset of mild diabetes and macrovascular problems. Other important risk factors for CHD, such as hyperlipidemia and hypertension, have causative links and frequently interact with smoking. The consequences of smoking are nearly identical or nearly identical to those of smoking. The goal of this article is to give a quick summary of the consequences of smoking on cardiovascular function, specifically the effects of nicotine and carbon monoxide (CO). Nicotine decreases independent cardiac function while increasing sympathetic activity and heart rate (HR).

Conclusion: By quitting smoking we have many options like behavioral changes and treatment instead of nicotine and bupropion.

Keywords: Tobacco smoke; nicotine; inflammation; free radicals.

1. INTRODUCTION

Smoking is one of the most preventable causes of death on the planet, and it is a leading cause of heart disease and death. Smoking is responsible for 25% of all heart disease deaths around the world. According to the European Society of Cardiology, smoking causes 28% of heart deaths in men aged 35 to 69 and 13% in women in the same age group. In the WHO's European Region, smoking is the second biggest risk factor for life expectancy due to disability and the highest risk factor for premature mortality, accounting for 1.6 million deaths each year. In the European Union, smoking is thought to be responsible for 15% of all deaths each year, and any smoking-related death among individuals aged 35 and over is considered homicide in Greece. The number of deaths due to old age, which accounts for 18.1 percent of all deaths, is also included [1].

Tobacco use kills about 6 million people each year, according to the World Health Organization, including over 600,000 smokers who die of heart disease, lung cancer, and other diseases. If current trends continue, it is estimated that more than 8 million people will die each year by 2030. Among other things, smoking is a leading cause of heart disease, ischemic stroke, peripheral artery disease, and gastrointestinal aneurysms. It has been associated with an increased risk of some malignancies and is one of the primary causes of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Active or passive smoking can cause heart disease through a range of interrelated pathways such as increased oxidative stress, hemodynamic changes, and autonomic flexibility. Side effects include endothelial dysfunction, thrombosis, inflammation, hyperlipidemia, and other problems. Even minor exposures, such as a few cigarettes per day, might have significant harmful consequences. Cigarette smoke contains over 4,000 chemicals that have been found to damage heart function [1].

Smoking exacerbates other cardiovascular risk factors such as fructose intolerance and low serum levels of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDLc). However, studies have shown that, in addition to the effects of smoking on other risk factors, smoking raises the risk of cardiovascular disease (CVD). To put it another way, if smoking doubles the risk level while also raising another risk factor, adjustments are done at the level of these other risk variables to

distinguish smokers from nonsmokers. The danger is predicted to quadruple. Even though smoking has been linked to PAD, aortic aneurysm, CHD, and cerebrovascular disease, the associated risk of disease (RR) differs depending on the arterial bed [1].

1.1 Aim of the Study

To understand the effects of smoking on the cardiovascular system and some knowledge about associated disorders thus you can manage it to decrease the suffering and prevent catastrophic death for the patient.

2. THE PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF CIGARETTE SMOKING AND CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE

Cigarette smoking (CS) continues to be a leading cause of morbidity and mortality from cardiovascular disease. Cigarette smoking affects atherosclerosis at every stage, from endothelial dysfunction to acute clinical events, the latter of which is predominantly thrombotic. Cigarette smoke exposure, both active and passive (environmental), increases the risk of cardiovascular events. It's unclear whether there's a clear dose-dependent link between cigarette smoke exposure and risk because some recent experimental clinical trials have demonstrated a non-linear association between cigarette smoke exposure and risk. CS causes inflammation, thrombosis, and LDL cholesterol oxidation, even though the particular harmful components of cigarette smoke and the processes of CS-related cardiovascular dysfunction are unknown. Recent experimental and clinical research supports the notion that cigarette smoke exposure increases oxidative stress, which may be a risk factor for cardiovascular disease [2].

Cigarette smoking (CS) increases the risk of myocardial infarction (MI) and fatal coronary artery disease in both men and women, according to epidemiological studies (CAD). When compared to nonsmokers, even low-tar cigarettes and smokeless tobacco have been shown to increase the risk of cardiovascular events. Furthermore, passive smoking (ambient tobacco exposure) with one-hundredth of the smoke exposure of active smoking is linked to a 30% increase in the risk of coronary artery disease, compared to an 80% increase in active smokers. While there is substantial evidence relating cigarette smoke exposure to

cardiovascular disease, the specific components of cigarette smoke, as well as the mechanisms that drive this link, are unknown. This article summarises the most recent clinical and

experimental findings on the pathobiology and mechanisms involved in smoking-related cardiovascular disease (Fig. 1) [3].

Fig. 1. Cigarette smoking-induced cardiovascular dysfunction: potential paths and causes. The flow diagram's bold boxes and arrows reflect the most likely central mechanisms in the complicated pathophysiology of the cigarette-smoking-mediated atherothrombotic illness. METC = mitochondrial electron transport chain; NADPH = nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate reduced form; NOS = nitric oxide synthase; ONOO= peroxynitrite; O2= superoxide; H2O2= hydrogen peroxide [3]

3. CARDIOVASCULAR EFFECTS

3.1 Sudden Death

CVD is the main cause of sudden mortality in the United States. In a detailed analysis integrating data from the Framingham Heart Study and the Albany Study, which looked at sudden cardiac mortality in males aged 45-64 years, smoking was found to be a statistically significant risk factor. In data analysis of the 1986 National Mortality Follow-up Survey of People Without a History of CHD, smoking was the only variable risk factor for sudden cardiac death, increasing the risk of sudden cardiac death in people with heart disease. It was connected to it in some way. Coronary Heart Disease (CHD) is an acronym for Coronary Heart Disease. In individuals with left ventricular dysfunction following a MI, there is a relationship between stopping smoking and a lower risk of cardiac arrhythmia death. Finally, smokers who survived cardiac arrest outside of the hospital had a decreased risk of recurrent cardiac arrest than nonsmokers [4].

3.2 Stroke

Compared to non-smokers, smokers had a greater incidence of cerebral palsy-related stroke, mortality, and a clear connection to volume response. Furthermore, according to 20-year prospective mortality research controlled for other risk variables connected to cardiovascular risk, smoking increases the incidence of stroke and increases death as the number of smokers increases. Former smokers younger than 75 years old had a higher risk of stroke than non-smokers in the same age group, according to a meta-analysis of data from 32 studies. Everyone of all ages is invited. Throughout the Framingham Heart Study's 26-year follow-up analysis, smoking was a major risk factor for stroke. Smokers who quit smoking for two years had a reduced risk than smokers who did not smoke for the rest of their lives after quitting for five years [5].

3.3 Aortic Aneurysm

In terms of vascular degeneration, arteriovenous arterial occlusion disease differs from atherosclerotic and other arterial occlusive illnesses. The pathological process of aneurysm formation in the vascular tree varies depending

on where it happens. An abdominal infrarenal aortic aneurysm (AAA) is the most common type of aneurysm, and smoking is the most dangerous risk factor. AAA is caused by smoking at a much higher incidence than atherosclerosis. Smoking not only contributes to the cause of AAA, but also accelerates the disease's course and increases the chance of fractures in those who already have it. To establish the mechanical relationship between AAA and smoke, advanced animals based on smoke or smoke components are used. Long-term alterations in the function of vascular smooth muscle cells and inflammatory cells are involved in the processes. This review will examine the clinical, epidemiological, and technical evidence considering tobacco as a cause of aneurysms, with an emphasis on AAA [6].

Arteriovenous arterial occlusion disease differs from arteriosclerosis and other arterial occlusive illnesses in terms of clinical, historical, and functional characteristics. Although atherosclerotic changes can occur in most aneurysms, this is not the cause. Aneurysms are more common in some arteries than others, and the causes of aneurysms vary depending on where they occur. Although there is some evidence that smoking contributes to the formation or advancement of some aneurysms, no research has been done on the role of smoking in the development or progression of other aneurysms [7].

3.4 Hypertension

Quitting smoking is one of the most effective ways to avoid many of these ailments, as it is a major risk factor for cardiovascular disease. Endothelial dysfunction, arteriosclerosis, inflammation, lipid conversion, antithrombotic and thrombosis-promoting changes, and antithrombotic and thrombosis-promoting changes are all key variables linked to smoking and the acceleration of atherosclerotic processes leading to cardiovascular events. By activating the sympathetic nervous system, smoking raises blood pressure (Fig. 2) [8].

3.5 Lipid Metabolism

The effects of smoking include changes in lipid metabolism with increased lipolysis, insulin resistance, and tissue lipotoxicity. Smoking is prothrombotic and atherogenic (Fig. 3) [9].

Fig. 2. (Hypertension pathogenesis) [8]

Disorders of lipid metabolism

Arterial walls.

- It is the most important manifestation of lipid disorders.
 - Cholesterol accumulation and associated cellular proliferation and fibrous tissue formation produces **atheromatous plaques**.
 - Atherosclerosis is due to deformation and obstruction of the artery that may result from calcification and ulceration of plaques.
- The small lipoproteins LDL and IDL are atherogenic.

Fig. 3. (Disruption of lipid metabolism in smokers) [9]

4. HEMODYNAMIC EFFECTS

4.1 Blood Pressure and Heart Rate

Nicotine stimulates the adrenal medulla and endothelial nerve terminals to produce adrenaline and norepinephrine, causing a rise in heart rate and maximum attenuation via myocardial β_1 receptor stimulation. Peripheral vascular resistance increases as a result of α_1 -receptor-mediated vasoconstriction, which raises

blood pressure. It also stimulates the β_2 and α_2 receptors in the coronary arteries. Activation of two receptors promotes vasodilation, while stimulation of two receptors promotes vasoconstriction [10].

4.2 Coronary Blood Flow

Smoking alters the response of coronary blood flow to increasing myocardial oxygen demand, resulting in a reduction in the flow of the coronary

vasodilator blood flow reserve. As a result, the increase in coronary blood flow is lower than would be expected in the absence of secondhand smoking exposure, based on myocardial function. Numerous studies have connected tobacco use to coronary artery endothelial dysfunction. A narrowing of the coronary arteries has been linked to smoking. While smoking improves blood flow in persons who do not have coronary heart disease, it can decrease cardiovascular blood flow in those who do [10].

4.3 Thrombogenic Effects

Smoke-induced thrombosis appears to play a big role in severe heart attacks and strokes. Aside from angina, epidemiological research suggests that smoking increases the risk of severe myocardial infarction and sudden death. The risk of severe myocardial infarction and sudden death is linked to thrombosis, according to researchers, and angina pectoris is predominantly caused by hemodynamic factors. Nonsmokers had a better likelihood of recovering from thrombin therapy than smokers [10].

4.4 Arteriosclerosis

If there is dynamic blood flow or endothelial damage, the prodromal step of atheromatous plaque formation could be the generation of platelets along the artery wall. Nicotine is thought

to increase blood viscosity and platelet aggregation because it inhibits the synthesis of prostacyclin, which may lessen platelet aggregation. Platelet adhesion promotes the formation of thrombi, separates coronary artery nerves, hastens the formation of atheromatous plaques, and has been linked to a higher risk of myocardial ischemia. Nicotine also changes prostaglandin metabolism, lowering vascular defenses against platelet aggregation (Fig. 4) [11].

Coronary heart disease (CHD), stroke, and peripheral arterial disease are all caused by atherosclerosis, a degenerative process that affects the coronary arteries, cerebral arteries, iliac and femoral arteries, and the aorta (PAD). In the intima of the major elastic and muscular arteries, lipid deposits in macrophages and smooth muscle cells, primarily cholesterol and its esters, begin in childhood. In early infancy, the lesions, known as fatty streaks, generate only modest intimal thickening and no blood flow problems, but they quickly develop after puberty. A core of lipid and necrotic debris is covered by a cap of smooth muscle and fibrous tissue in young adults, and a core of lipid and necrotic debris is covered by a cap of smooth muscle and fibrous tissue in young adults. Fibrous plaques are raised lesions that protrude into the lumen and, as a result of these alterations, hinder blood flow [11].

Fig. 4. (Atherosclerosis in smokers) [11]

4.5 Endothelial Affection

Endothelial cells have been shown to secrete inflammatory and proatherogenic cytokines in response to smoke exposure. Endothelial dysfunction is the result of all of these events. Endothelial cell loss occurs owing to apoptosis or necrosis as a result of the direct physiological effects of smoke chemicals and the generation of active forms of oxygen (ROS) (Fig. 5) [12].

4.6 Inflammation

Studies suggest that inflammation affects atherosclerosis as high leukocyte counts and high CRP and fibrinogen levels are potent predictors of future cardiovascular events. However, the mechanism by which tobacco smoking promotes inflammation has not been fully elucidated (Fig. 6) [13].

Fig. 5. (Endothelial damage in smokers) [12]

Fig. 6. (Inflammation pathogenesis in smokers) [13]

4.7 Smoking and Diabetes

Smoking has been demonstrated in numerous studies to have a deleterious impact on glucose and lipid metabolism in both with and without diabetes. According to the researchers, smoking in diabetes patients was linked to poor metabolic management, as well as an elevated risk of microvascular and macrovascular problems, as well as death (Fig. 7) [14].

Fig. 7. (How smoking causes diabetes) [14]

5. COMPLICATIONS

5.1 Microvascular Complications

In both type 1 and type 2 diabetes, microvascular complications (retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy) are linked to metabolic management. Although numerous pathogenic processes have been hypothesised, the

Fig. 8. (Microvascular complications of smoking) [15]

mechanisms of microvascular disease development are not entirely understood. Hyperglycemia acts as a catalyst for downstream events such as aldose reductase's conversion of glucose to sorbitol, non-enzymatic glycosylation of proteins and receptors in afflicted tissues, increased oxidative stress, and activation of protein kinase C and mitogen-activated protein kinases (Figs. 7, 8) [15].

5.2 Nephropathy

Smoking and hyperglycemia increase oxidative stress and lipid accumulation, which regulates TGF- β , accumulates AGEs, reduces nitric oxide production, leads to inflammation of the lower glomerular membrane and mesangial proliferation, and further progression of mesangial glomerulosclerosis and interstitial fibrosis, as well as the effects of fibrosis (Fig. 9) [15].

5.3 Retinopathy

In general, researchers have never considered smoking to be a major risk factor for diabetic retinopathy. The results of a very large multicenter study show no strong support for such associations, except in the elderly with certain medical conditions. However, at least two studies of patients with type 1 diabetes suggest that smoking prioritizes patients with this retinopathy (Fig. 10) [16].

Fig. 9. (How smoking causes diabetic nephropathy) [15]

Fig. 10. (Effect of smoking on the eye) [16]

5.4 Neuropathy

Smoking affects blood circulation and can increase the risk of peripheral neuropathy. Care should be taken in foot care, as peripheral neuropathy can begin slowly with numbness in the feet. Check your feet daily for cuts and other wounds (Fig. 11) [17].

5.5 Macrovascular Complications

Diabetic people are more likely to develop smoking-related diseases, as well as coronary artery disease and death. Smokers with type 1 or type 2 diabetes did not significantly enhance their risk of CHD in a research group in London,

England, according to the Multinational Study of Vascular Diseases of Diabetes, which was supported by the World Health Organization. The Stroke Diabetes and Complication Management Study (New England Journal of Medicine, 1993) looked examined the role of intensive insulin therapy and glycemic-controlled therapy in type 1 diabetes and concluded that after an eighth year, smoking was not a major risk factor for macrovascular complications. This study was not well constructed to investigate the role of cigarette usage since the subjects were relatively few. According to certain research, smoking increases the risk of CHD in young persons with type 1 diabetes (Fig. 12) [18].

Fig. 11. (Effect of smoking on neurons) [17]

Fig. 12. (Macrovascular complications of smoking) [18]

6. FIRST, SECOND AND THIRD HAND SMOKE EFFECTS

Smoking's risks are well-known. Inhaling nicotine and other harmful chemicals in cigarette smoke can lead to heart disease, stroke, and lung cancer in both smokers and nonsmokers. The impact of "thirdhand smoke," which refers to the potentially cancer-causing substances formed when tobacco smoke particles combine with gases in the air and permeate into surrounding surfaces such as carpets, rugs, garments, bed sheets, wall paint, car dashboards, and even toys, is less well understood. Tobacco smoke residue can linger in these materials for years after a cigarette has been extinguished, raising concerns among scientists that this could be hazardous to people's health. However, determining the hazards of thirdhand smoking is

challenging, and there is little data on the implications [19].

Thirdhand smoke is created when particles from a cigarette or other tobacco-burning device enter and permeate into things such as hair, clothes, furniture, carpet, and walls. The compounds are then aged, which changes their chemical structure. When nicotine reacts with indoor air pollutants like nitrous acid, it forms carcinogens, or compounds that might cause cancer. The gas is periodically re-emitted into the air in a process known as "off-gassing" [20]. Opening windows or using a fan to disperse smoke will not prevent thirdhand smoke from forming or being absorbed, and the residue will continue to release hazardous chemicals for years, if not decades. thirdhand smoking isn't a one-time occurrence. "It's a phenomenon that develops

over time as a result of increased exposure." Standard cleaning procedures do not affect contaminants. In most circumstances, the only options are to replace the carpets or repaint the walls [21].

Thirdhand smoking has been a research focus for decades, even though it is a relatively new phrase. Painting mice with tobacco smoke condensate—or liquid from gas condensation—caused cancer, according to a doctor from Washington University School of Medicine in St. Louis in 1953. Researchers discovered nicotine in the dust of smokers' homes in a 1991 investigation. Researchers discovered that nicotine was still present in residences where smokers attempted to reduce their exposure by smoking outside in a 2004 study. Cigarette residue on the dashboards of cars driven by smokers who had outlawed smoking in their vehicles, according to a 2008 study comparing smokers' and non-smokers' automobiles [22].

After being initially used in a 2009 article published in *Pediatrics*, the term "thirdhand smoke" became well-known. The authors theorized that "children are more vulnerable to thirdhand smoke exposure because they breathe near, crawl and play on, touch, and mouth polluted surfaces," and that "children are more vulnerable to thirdhand smoke exposure because they breathe near, crawl and play on, touch, and mouth polluted surfaces." The American Academy of Pediatricians made suggestions for minimizing children's exposure to reduce the risk. "Smokers should be aware of this," Dr. Bechara says, "since it may serve as an incentive for them to quit for the sake of their loved ones." "Becoming conscious of thirdhand smoke may assist smokers in realizing that they are potentially damaging others as well as themselves" [23].

7. DIFFERENT TYPES OF SMOKING IN ASIAN COUNTRIES

In India, Pakistan, Nepal, and Bangladesh, there were also hookah (sheesha), bidi, and cigars; cigars in the Philippines; hand-rolled tobacco in Timor Leste; Pan Masala and Gutkha in India; and nuswar in Pakistan. If they responded 'yes' to the first question, 'pipe' to the fourth question, or smoked hookah, bidi, cigars, or hand-rolled tobacco, they were classed as 'current smokers.' If respondents answered the fourth question with any sort of SLT, such as 'chewing' tobacco, 'Pan

Masala,' 'Gutkha,' and snuff,' they were classed as 'current SLT users' [23].

8. METHODS TO REDUCE EXPOSURE

Evidence-based methods for treating smokers include behavioural and pharmacological treatments that drastically boost rates of long-term abstinence from smoking. Despite this, absolute abstinence rates are low, ranging between 8% and 25% depending on the study group and treatment. Furthermore, at any given time, only a tiny percentage of smokers are interested in treatment. Patients with CVD are more motivated to quit smoking and have a higher chance of remaining smoke-free for a long time than the general public. Despite this, abstinence rates remain dismally low, especially considering the significant health benefits of stopping smoking for this group [23].

Researchers want to know if any strategies could reduce the risk of smoking among patients who continue to smoke due to poor treatment outcomes. Despite the lack of evidence that lowering cigarette exposure reduces harm, these initiatives are referred to as "harm reduction" strategies. To present, only a few clinical trials, prospective cohort studies, and epidemiologic studies have looked at the efficacy of exposure reduction methods on CVD risk factors and development [23].

Thrombosis (e.g., fibrinogen and PAI-1); lipid abnormalities (e.g., total cholesterol, HDLc, LDLc, triglycerides, APOs A-I and B, and HDLc to LDLc ratio); and oxidative stress (e.g., total cholesterol, HDLc, LDLc, triglycerides, APOs A-I and B, and HDLc to LDLc (blood pressure, heart rate, angina, exercise tolerance, MI, other adverse events, and death) [24].

9. EPIDEMIOLOGY

Even though low- and middle-income nations account for more than 80% of worldwide cardiovascular disease burden, wealthier countries are more aware of the influence of risk factors. As a result, in most parts of the world, the impact of such factors on the risk of coronary heart disease is unknown (25). A case-control study of acute myocardial infarction was constructed in 52 countries that represented every continent inhabited. A total of 15152 patients and 14820 controls were enrolled in the study. This study looks into the relationship between smoking, hypertension, diabetes,

waist/hip ratio, dietary habits, physical activity, alcohol use, blood apolipoproteins (Apo), and psychosocial factors, as well as myocardial infarction. Using odds ratios and their 95 percent confidence intervals, the connection of risk variables to myocardial infarction and their population attributable risks (PAR) was estimated [25].

Smoking (odds ratio 2.87 for current vs never, PAR 35.7% for current and former vs never), raised ApoB/ApoA1 ratio (3.25 for top vs lowest quintile, PAR 49.2% for top four quintiles vs lowest quintile), history of hypertension (1.91, PAR 17.9%), diabetes (2.37, PAR 9.9%), abdominal obesity (1.12 for top vs lowest tertile and 1.62 for middle vs lowest tertile, PAR 20.1% for top two tertiles vs lowest tertile), psychosocial factors (2.67, PAR 32.5%), daily consumption of fruits and vegetables (0.70, PAR 13.7% for lack of daily consumption), regular alcohol consumption (0.91, PAR 6.7%), and regular physical activity (0.86, PAR 12.2%), were all significantly related to acute myocardial infarction ($p < 0.0001$ for all risk factors and $p = 0.03$ for alcohol). These connections were found in both men and women, young and old, and in all parts of the globe. In men, these nine risk factors accounted for 90% of the PAR, while in women, they accounted for 94% [26]. Abnormal lipids, smoking, hypertension, diabetes, abdominal obesity, psychosocial variables, consumption of fruits, vegetables, and alcohol, and regular physical exercise all contribute to the majority of the risk of myocardial infarction in both sexes and at all ages in all places. This research suggests that global preventative programs can be built on similar principles and can prevent the majority of myocardial infarctions before they happen [27].

10. DISCUSSION

Tobacco kills one person every six seconds, or one adult in ten. Tobacco-related diseases will kill up to half of today's smokers in the future. Around 80% of the world's over 1 billion smokers live in low- and middle-income countries, where tobacco-related diseases and deaths are much more common. Around the world, an estimated 6 million people die each year as a result of the impacts of smoking. Approximately half of all children are regularly exposed to cigarette smoke in public places. More than 40% of children are exposed to secondhand smoke because at least one parent smokes. Secondhand smoking causes the deaths of 600,000 individuals each

year. According to the Eurobarometer report "European Attitude Tobacco" from 2012, 28 percent of Europeans aged 15 and older smoke, with Greece having the highest prevalence (40 percent) and Sweden having the lowest (13 percent). Italy (together with the Netherlands) is in fourth place, with a 24 percent increase in frequency since last time. The Istituto Superiore di Sanita, which commissions the DOXA survey every year, observed a low rate of 21% in 2012 [28].

In Egypt, cigarettes are smoked by 37.7% of men, 0.5 percent of women, and a total of 19.4 percent (9.6 million adults). Every day, 35.8% of men and 0.5 percent of women in the United States smoke cigarettes. 6.2 percent of men, 0.3 percent of women, and a total of 3.3 percent of the population use hookah (1.6 million adults). 6.5 million people inhale secondhand smoking (60.7 percent of adults whose workplace includes their home). Another research found that 19% of high school pupils in Egypt's suburbs have ever smoked hookah. According to three surveys, 11-15 percent of elderly men in the valleys smoke in pipe clubs. Smoking is also very common among medical professionals and students. According to a 2010 study, smoking prevalence among healthcare workers in Italy is 44 percent, more than double that of the general population, and this is attributed solely to an increase in the number of nurses (48.2 percent). Doctors (33, 9%), medical students. (35%) and graduate students (52.9%) [29].

Nicotine, carbon monoxide (CO), oxidizing gases, and other components of cigarette smoke, including atherogenesis in CVD pathogenesis, have all received a lot of attention as contributing factors to CVD. After each cigarette, nicotine, which is rapidly absorbed from cigarette smoke, is present in blood at quantities of 40 to 100 ng/ml. In most cases, 1 to 2 milligrams of nicotine are consumed in a methodical manner per cigarette (mg). This pattern of deposition is linked to the end of nicotine's two-hour half-life. Nicotine levels in smokers' venous plasma reach an all-time high early in the morning and remain there until bedtime. As a result of these discoveries, the average smoker is exposed to high quantities of nicotine 24 hours a day. Nicotine stimulates the release of catecholamines from neurons and the adrenal gland on a local level. In studies of the pharmacodynamics of nicotine, the severity of its main effects is more rapid [30].

11. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The largest preventable cause of cardiovascular illness and mortality is cigarette smoking. Smoking has been linked to a two- to fourfold increased risk of coronary heart disease, a 70 percent excess rate of coronary heart disease death, and an increased risk of sudden death. These risks are exacerbated by hypertension, hypercholesterolemia, glucose intolerance, and diabetes, which all have a synergistic effect with smoking. There is also a well-established association between smoking and the chance of developing peripheral vascular disease. Smokers account for over 70% of patients with atherosclerosis obliterans and nearly all of those with thromboangiitis obliterans. The link between smoking and cerebrovascular illness is still being contested, even though smokers have a higher risk of stroke and stroke-related death than nonsmokers. Although smoking has been linked to the development of cor pulmonale, there is no evidence that it causes congestive heart failure.

Nicotine and carbon monoxide appears to be significant players in smoking's detrimental effects on the cardiovascular system. Both components have been shown to influence the myocardial oxygen supply/demand ratio and cause endothelial injury, resulting in atherosclerotic plaque development. There have also been unfavorable effects on the lipid profile, albeit no link has been shown between these alterations and the risk of cardiovascular disease. Smoking cessation, in particular, reduced the risk of death from coronary heart disease and stroke significantly. Given that smoking rates in the United States have fallen disproportionately among the educated, future efforts must concentrate on offering effective education, including smoking cessation tools, to the less educated.

CONSENT

It is not applicable.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

It is not applicable.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

REFERENCES

1. Alberg AJ, Shopland DR, Cummings KM. The 2014 Surgeon General's report: Commemorating the 50th Anniversary of the 1964 Report of the Advisory Committee to the US Surgeon General and updating the evidence on the health consequences of cigarette smoking. *Am J Epidemiol.* 2014 Feb 15;179(4):403-12.
2. Alexandrov LB, Ju YS, Haase K, Van Loo P, Martincorena I, Nik-Zainal S, et al. Mutational signatures associated with tobacco smoking in human cancer. *Science.* 2016 Nov 04;354(6312):618-622.
3. Ambrose JA, Barua RS. The pathophysiology of cigarette smoking and cardiovascular disease: an update. *J Am Coll Cardiol.* 2004 May 19;43(10):1731-7.
4. Balbo S, Turesky RJ, Villalta PW. DNA adductomics. *Chem Res Toxicol.* 2014 Mar 17;27(3):356-66.
5. Budani MC, Fensore S, Di Marzio M, Tiboni GM. Cigarette smoking impairs clinical outcomes of assisted reproductive technologies: A meta-analysis of the literature. *Reprod Toxicol.* 2018 Sep;80:49-59.
6. Clinical Practice Guideline Treating Tobacco Use and Dependence 2008 Update Panel, Liaisons, and Staff. A clinical practice guideline for treating tobacco use and dependence: 2008 update. A U.S. Public Health Service report. *Am J Prev Med.* 2008 Aug;35(2):158-76.
7. de Micheli A. [The tobacco in the light of history and medicine]. *Arch Cardiol Mex.* 2015 Oct-Dec;85(4):318-22.
8. Duffy SA, Ignacio RV, Kim HM, Geraci MC, Essenmacher CA, Hall SV, et al. Effectiveness of tobacco cessation pharmacotherapy in the Veterans Health Administration. *Tob Control.* 2019 Sep;28(5):540-547.
9. Duffy SA, Ronis DL, Karvonen-Gutierrez CA, Ewing LA, Dalack GW, Smith PM, Carmody TP, Hicks T, Hermann C, Reeves P, Flanagan P. Effectiveness of the tobacco tactics program in the Department of Veterans Affairs. *Ann Behav Med.* 2014 Oct;48(2):265-74.
10. Fox CS, Coady S, Sorlie PD, Levy D, Meigs JB, D'Agostino RB, Wilson PW, Savage PJ. Trends in cardiovascular complications of diabetes. *JAMA.* 2004 Nov 24;292(20):2495-9.

11. Fox CS, Pencina MJ, Wilson PW, Paynter NP, Vasan RS, D'Agostino RB. Lifetime risk of cardiovascular disease among individuals with and without diabetes stratified by obesity status in the Framingham heart study. *Diabetes Care*. 2008 Aug;31(8):1582-4.
12. Gowing LR, Ali RL, Allsop S, Marsden J, Turf EE, West R, Witton J. Global statistics on addictive behaviours: 2014 status report. *Addiction*. 2015 Jun;110(6):904-19.
13. Jaén Díaz JI, de Castro Mesa C, Gontán García-Salamanca MJ, López de Castro F. [Prevalence of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and risk factors in smokers and ex-smokers]. *Arch Bronconeumol*. 2003 Dec;39(12):554-8.
14. Jha P, Ramasundarahettige C, Landsman V, Rostron B, Thun M, Anderson RN, McAfee T, Peto R. 21st-century hazards of smoking and benefits of cessation in the United States. *N Engl J Med*. 2013 Jan 24;368(4):341-50.
15. King AC, Cao D, O'Malley SS, Kranzler HR, Cai X, deWit H, Matthews AK, Stachowiak RJ. Effects of naltrexone on smoking cessation outcomes and weight gain in nicotine-dependent men and women. *J Clin Psychopharmacol*. 2012 Oct;32(5):630-6.
16. Kovac JR, Khanna A, Lipshultz LI. The effects of cigarette smoking on male fertility. *Postgrad Med*. 2015 Apr;127(3):338-41.
17. Laniado-Laborín R. Smoking and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Parallel epidemics of the 21 century. *Int J Environ Res Public Health*. 2009 Jan; 6(1):209-24.
18. Li Y, Lin H, Li Y, Cao J. Association between socio-psycho-behavioral factors and male semen quality: systematic review and meta-analyses. *Fertil Steril*. 2011 Jan;95(1):116-23.
19. Lloyd-Jones DM, Hong Y, Labarthe D, Mozaffarian D, Appel LJ, Van Horn L, et al. American Heart Association Strategic Planning Task Force and Statistics Committee. Defining and setting national goals for cardiovascular health promotion and disease reduction: The American Heart Association's strategic Impact Goal through 2020 and beyond. *Circulation*. 2010 Feb 02;121(4):586-613.
20. Miller EC. Some current perspectives on chemical carcinogenesis in humans and experimental animals: Presidential Address. *Cancer Res*. 1978 Jun;38(6):1479-96.
21. Mineshita M, Kida H, Handa H, Nishine H, Furuya N, Inoue T, Matsuoka S, Miyazawa T. Regional Lung Sound Asynchrony in Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease Patients. *Respiration*. 2016;92(4):252-257.
22. Pereira PP, Da Mata FA, Figueiredo AC, de Andrade KR, Pereira MG. Maternal Active Smoking During Pregnancy and Low Birth Weight in the Americas: A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis. *Nicotine Tob Res*. 2017 May 01;19(5):497-505.
23. Stead LF, Buitrago D, Preciado N, Sanchez G, Hartmann-Boyce J, Lancaster T. Physician advice for smoking cessation. *Cochrane Database Syst Rev*. 2013 May 31;(5):CD000165.
24. Stratton K, Shetty P, Wallace R, Bondurant S. Clearing the smoke: the science base for tobacco harm reduction--executive summary. *Tob Control*. 2001 Jun;10(2):189-95.
25. Tindle HA, Stevenson Duncan M, Greevy RA, Vasan RS, Kundu S, Massion PP, Freiberg MS. Lifetime Smoking History and Risk of Lung Cancer: Results from the Framingham Heart Study. *J Natl Cancer Inst*. 2018 Nov 01;110(11):1201-1207.
26. Curry SJ, Krist AH, Owens DK, Barry MJ, Caughey AB, Davidson KW, et al. US Preventive Services Task Force. Risk Assessment for Cardiovascular Disease with Nontraditional Risk Factors: US Preventive Services Task Force Recommendation Statement. *JAMA*. 2018 Jul 17;320(3):272-280.
27. Wang TW, Asman K, Gentzke AS, Cullen KA, Holder-Hayes E, Reyes-Guzman C, Jamal A, Neff L, King BA. Tobacco Product Use Among Adults - United States, 2017. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep*. 2018 Nov 09;67(44):1225-1232.
28. Warren GW, Alberg AJ, Kraft AS, Cummings KM. The 2014 Surgeon General's report: The health consequences of smoking--50 years of progress: A paradigm shift in cancer care. *Cancer*. 2014 Jul 01;120(13):1914-6.
29. Yano M, Miura S, Shiga Y, Miyase Y, Suematsu Y, Norimatsu K, Nakamura A, Adachi S, Nishikawa H, Saku K. Association between smoking habits and severity of coronary stenosis as assessed by coronary computed tomography

- angiography. Heart Vessels. 2016 Jul;31(7):1061-8.
30. Zhang L, Wang XH, Zheng XM, Liu TZ, Zhang WB, Zheng H, Chen MF. Maternal gestational smoking, diabetes, alcohol drinking, pre-pregnancy obesity and the risk of cryptorchidism: A systematic review and meta-analysis of observational studies. PLoS One. 2015;10(3): e0119006.

© 2022 Elsaka and Ghazali; This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

Peer-review history:

The peer review history for this paper can be accessed here:
<https://www.sdiarticle5.com/review-history/78455>